

TEACHING METHODOLOGY IN HIGHER NON- PHILOLOGICAL DIRECTIONS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10418439>

ARTICLE INFO

Qabul qilindi: 10-December 2023 yil
Ma'qullandi: 15- December 2023 yil
Nashr qilindi: 21- December 2023 yil

KEY WORDS

Non-philological higher education, Russian language as a foreign language, teaching methodology, technologies, method.

ABSTRACT

In this article, the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language in non-philology higher education was considered. A comprehensive review of scientific and methodological literature was given. In order to generalize the accumulated theoretical and practical experience and apply it to the optimization of the educational process: issues of general teaching methodology, study of the text and its typology, study of reading, study of oral scientific discourse, new computer technologies were founded.

Methodology is a theoretical and practical science, in which the teacher's art, his ability to adapt general methodological recommendations to specific educational conditions is always of great importance.

In the higher education of non-philology, the subject of Russian as a language of study is taken as a system of linguistic phenomena, not for the purpose of describing it, but as a means of communication in written and oral form. Therefore, for this category of students, the methodology forms the task of learning Russian to participate in language communication, that is, the task of teaching speech activities in Russian: reading, speaking, listening, writing. This is a subject we need to explore. Such an approach to education in methodological science is called communicative.

Currently, the Russian language is taught as a foreign language in almost all non-philological higher education. Among other subjects of general education, the Russian language is a compulsory subject for foreign students of preparatory faculties, as well as students of specialization, bachelors, masters, graduate students, interns.

For 50 years, foreign students of non-philological higher education have been trained as a separate contingent in our country. The educational profile is "a priority type of teaching foreign students in the Russian language and other subjects, depending on their professional interests, their needs for the Russian language and the duration of their studies." The main distinguishing feature of higher education in non-philology is the approach to learning the Russian language as a means of mastering the chosen specialty.

Undoubtedly, non-philology has become one of the main directions of the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language in higher education. This happens for various reasons.

There are several main directions presented in the scientific and methodological literature in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language to students of non-philology higher education. These are:

- general methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language in non-philology higher education;
- research and analysis of text, its structure and units with text typology;
- study oral scientific-written speech;
- the process of learning to read;
- new computer technologies.

Let's dwell on the methodology of teaching students in non-philology higher education.

In the 1970s, one of the fundamental works in this regard is the book "Scientific style of speech: educational problems" by O. D. Mitrofanova. Linguistic and methodological foundations of teaching Russian as a foreign language are considered in the article. Also, answers to the following questions are given: when to start specialization, on which texts - general scientific, popular scientific or highly specialized - teaching; what is the role of terminological dictionary, what system of exercises should be offered to make learning more effective. The specific features of the style of scientific speech, its lexical composition and morphological and syntactic features of scientific speech are determined in sufficient detail; typology of texts is presented.

We highlight a few provisions that, in our opinion, are particularly relevant at this time. O. D. Mitrofanova draws attention to the fact that the Russian language is mandatory, but not the leading subject in any non-philological universities, because the main educational goal should be "educating qualified specialists with a broad scientific outlook, sufficient knowledge and perception of reality." The main goal of education, according to the author, is to understand practical rules and speech practice.

A new stage in the development of the theory of teaching students in non-philology higher education E.I. Motina "Language and specialization: linguo-methodical foundations of teaching the Russian language to non-philologists". This scientific work is devoted to the problem of forming a language base for non-philological students. The researcher believes that it is appropriate to organize the process of teaching the specialized language to students based on the speech material of the studied subjects. I fully agree with the author's opinion that "non-specialist language teaching should be based on the material of a specific field of scientific knowledge... and the material should be presented in the form in which it is embodied in this field of science." 'candle. At the same time, E.I. According to Motina, the teacher of the Russian language should not follow the teacher of science and work on the basis of the material learned in specialized classes, but it is necessary to separate and work with sample texts for each major subject.

In this case, a new question arises for researchers and methodologists: what characteristics should a typical text have? Answer L.P. We find in the work of Klobukova "Teaching a non-specialist language", where the text serves as the highest unit of such education. The author argues that the lesson justifies the use of any type of text at any stage of learning. When creating a text, the following features should be taken into account: "functional-semantic type of the text; the main topic of the presentation in the text and the angle of its consideration; text theme and problems; belonging of the text to a certain

functional-stylistic register; form of speech (oral or written); text presentation method; the number of communicators creating the text; text genre; level of adaptation of the text".

With the emergence of science-oriented textbooks and manuals of Russian as a foreign language, the question arises about the place and role of the educational dictionary in the process of teaching the subtleties of the language or specialty. T.I. Trubnikova proposes a system for describing specialized subtypes, describes the methodology of using such dictionaries to study the lexical and grammatical means of specialized subtypes and develop various types of speech activity, and also defines the criteria for creating a Russian dictionary on the basis of a specialized vocabulary. According to the researcher, "the educational vocabulary of the specialty... should be created by Russian language teachers together with subject specialists under the general methodological guidance of Russian specialists. The specialized educational dictionary should combine the characteristics of an encyclopedic and explanatory dictionary with the thematic principle of material placement.

In our opinion, a specialized educational vocabulary is not just a necessary thing, but a mandatory tool for training future specialists. Students of higher education in non-philology must constantly refer to such a dictionary to clarify special terms or new words at any stage of their education, therefore, the criteria for creating a specialized dictionary, based on the selection of language units, Russian as a foreign language are important problems of teaching methodology.

Teaching oral scientific speech to non-philology students is an important task, as well as teaching written speech, since 1990 it has been discussed by methodologists and researchers. In particular, T.G. Kopytkova proposed a method of teaching dialogic communication to students of non-philological universities. To implement the author's methodology, he developed a system of exercises: conditional communicative, non-communicative and truly communicative. Taking into account that the conditions of the tasks should create in the student not only a certain speech reaction, but also the ability to implement the communication process, adapt in a team, in an unfamiliar environment, the author creates a set of exercises for teaching dialogic communication.

Teaching to read is one of the main directions in non-philological higher educational institutions. Methodology of teaching to read by T.V. Astakhova, L. Bartoshevich, S.A. Vishnyakova, I.K. Gapochka, I.I. Zasadskaya, B.L. Imnadze, Z.I. Klychnikova, E.L. Korchagin, M.I. Pavlenko, N.V. Pirotti, E.S. Troyanskaya, S.K. There are many methods and educational manuals developed by Folomkin and others. Thus, Z.I. Klychnikova is dedicated to the psychology of reading. The author describes the opinions of local and foreign methodologists on the psychology of reading and reveals methodical methods of teaching reading. After him Z.I. Klychnikova, we emphasize that the font used for writing text in textbooks is of great importance in teaching reading. The type of font, styles (regular, italic, bold, underlined, etc.) have a psychological effect on the reader, depending on which they facilitate or complicate the process of perceiving and understanding the semantic content of the text.

By the end of the 2000s, he further summarized and systematized the existing information on teaching reading in Russian at a non-linguistic university. S.K. Folomkin. Based on the fact that reading in professional activities serves to satisfy the cognitive needs of professionals more than communicative, the author emphasizes the theory and practice of teaching reading, in particular: he describes reading as a type of speech activity, tasks and

main considers the tasks, thus the principles of teaching to read, determines the requirements for educational materials, describes the types of reading, gives exercises for mastering the components of reading. Therefore, teaching reading in the methodology of teaching Russian as a foreign language remains one of the main directions of training specialists in non-linguistic universities.

In recent years, a great deal of attention has been paid to socio-cultural, linguistic-cultural and linguistic approaches in the theory and practice of teaching Russian as a foreign language in non-linguistic higher educational institutions. Vocational education becomes impossible in the modern world without intercultural dialogue.

It should be said that at the current stage, personnel training in non-linguistic higher educational institutions is more pragmatic. Students determine the level of knowledge of the Russian language very well and know exactly where they will apply their professional knowledge, how much this knowledge is needed for them.

The practical results of this direction were the following: the emergence of a language teaching environment in universities and institutes (e-learning); creation of electronic classes, virtual classes, day and distance courses, teleconferences, webinars, electronic collections of educational texts; the development of multimedia teaching-methodical complexes, complex teaching manuals on linguistics and local studies, etc. has begun.

Today, priority is given to smart technologies (Smart Education) in teaching Russian as a foreign language. Researchers are interested in the following issues: designing a smart textbook of Russian as a foreign language, possibilities of using mobile technologies in teaching Russian, web quest has been developed as a form of organizing students' independent work.

Thus, at present, the use of computer technologies is not only a necessary, but also a mandatory component of the process of linguistic education at a non-philological university. All the above-mentioned aspects and directions of teaching Russian as a foreign language at a non-philological university are proof of the considerable scientific and methodological experience accumulated in this regard. However, at present, there are big changes related to the emergence of new contingents of students, reduction of class time, presence of students of different ages in study groups, increase in the number of groups, new communication needs of students. Accordingly, there are new aspects of methods, principles, teaching manuals of teaching Russian as a foreign language. In any case, a teacher working in a non-philological higher educational institution should rely on the accumulated scientific and pedagogical experience and go further in search of new content-organizational and linguistic-methodical solutions to optimize the educational process.

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